

Virú State Religion

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The Virú State was a first-generation state (i.e., a state formation that evolves without contact with other states, see Spencer 2010) that developed in the Virú Valley, North Coast of Peru, between about 200 BCE and 700 CE. This state first unified the Virú Valley into a single political entity, establishing a four-tiered settlement hierarchy. At the top of this settlement hierarchy was the political capital of the Gallinazo Group, a large (ca. 10,000-14,000 people) urban center featuring civic-ceremonial and residential structures. In the first four centuries CE, the state expanded northward to the Moche and Chicama valleys, establishing a number of outposts. The development and growth of the huaca centers following Moche ideology (see Quilter and Koons 2012) caused the retreat of the Virú State in its homeland. Towards the end of its trajectory (ca. 500-700 CE), possible social and political changes led to the emergence of a new political center in the valley Huancaco, which was abandoned after a strong El Niño event (Bourget 2003; Bourget 2010; Downey 2014; Espinosa et al. 2021; Millaire 2010; Millaire and Eastaugh 2011; Millaire and Eastaugh 2014; Millaire et al. 2016). Even though no written source about this political formation and its people is available, information gathered during archaeological excavations may shed some light on the Virú State's religious practices.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 700 CE

Region: Virú State

Region tags: Peru

The Virú State at its maximum expansion (ca. 1-400 CE)

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The emergence of Moche huaca centers in the Chicama and Moche valleys may have created a competitive religious environment. Eventually, Moche ideology prevailed (Billman 1996; Millaire et al. 2016; Quilter and Koons 2012).

Reference: Billman, Brian R.. "The Evolution of Prehistoric Political Organizations in the Moche

Valley, Peru". PhD Thesis, University of California, 1996.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016–25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey, and Michele Koons. "The Fall of the Moche: A Critique of Claims for South America's First State". *Latin American Antiquity* 23, no. 2 (June 2012): 127–43. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.23.2.127>.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear if there were conflicts between people that adhered to the cults of the Viru' State and Moche huaca centers, the desecration of Viru' burials at Pampa La Cruz in the Moche Valley indicates at least some tensions (see Sanchez Chuyo 2021; Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Millaire et al. 2016).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016–25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As in many other Prehispanic Andean groups, religion and politics were likely intertwined (see Quilter 2022: 43).

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey. *The Ancient Central Andes*. 2nd ed.. Routledge, 2022.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 29658

Notes: The number refers to the intermediate estimate (250 people/ha) proposed by Downey (2014: 147) for the whole Viru' Valley. The lowest estimate is 11,863 (100 people/ha), while the high estimate is 42,708 (360 people/ha). During the apogee of the Viru' state (1-400 CE), the number of people part of this political unit and associated cult was likely larger.

Reference: Downey, Jordan T.. *Statecraft in the Virú Valley, Peru, in the First Millennium A.D.*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2014. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2687/>.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Notes: but see relationship with Moche

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey, and Michele Koons. "The Fall of the Moche: A Critique of Claims for South America's First State". *Latin American Antiquity* 23, no. 2 (June 2012): 127-43. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.23.2.127>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016-25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: *Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection*, 2010.

Reference: Makowski, Krzysztof. "Virú-moche Relations: Technological Identity, Stylistic Preferences,

and the Ethnic Identity of Ceramic Manufacturers and Users". In *Gallinazo: An Early Cultural Tradition on the Peruvian North Coast*, edited by Jean-François Millaire and Magali Morlion, 33–61. Los Angeles, CA: UCLA Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2009. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2tk8b0wc>.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 10000

Notes: This is the approximate size of the main ceremonial mound located at Huaca Gallinazo (the capital of the Viru' state), which covers about 17 ha/170,000 square meters (V-59, see Downey 2014; Millaire and Eastaugh 2011; Millaire and Eastaugh 2014; Willey 1953).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Edward Eastaugh. "Ancient Urban Morphology in the Virú Valley, Peru: Remote Sensing Work at the Gallinazo Group (100 B.C.–A.D. 700)". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 36, no. 4 (2011): 289–97. <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346911X13200731373908>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Edward Eastaugh. "Geophysical Survey on the Coast of Peru: The Early Prehispanic City of Gallinazo Group in the Viru Valley". *Latin American Antiquity* 25, no. 3 (September 2014): 239–55. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.25.3.239>.

Reference: Downey, Jordan T.. *Statecraft in the Virú Valley, Peru, in the First Millennium A.D.*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2014. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2687/>.

Reference: Willey, Gordon R.. *Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Peru*. Vol. 155. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution, 1953. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/15450>.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 25

Notes: This is the height of the main mound at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 (Viru' Valley) noted in the 1940s by Gordon Willey (1953: 132). It must be noted that the monument has been eroded and heavily looted during Colonial and Modern times.

Reference: Willey, Gordon R.. Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Peru. Vol. 155. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution, 1953. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/15450>.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Viru' deceased were buried in simple pits dug in the ground (in some cases outlined by stone slabs - see Larco Hoyle 1945) rather than in monumental tombs. As specified in Beliefs - Burial and Afterlife, in some cases people were wrapped in textiles and placed on reed mates/caskets. Burials were identified at various sites, such as Huaca Gallinazo V-59 (Bennett 1950; Millaire and La Torre 2011; Strong and Evans 1952; Willey 1953), Huaca Santa Clara (Dillon 2015; Millaire 2010; Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2003), and Huancaco (Bourget 2003; Bourget 2010) in the Viru' Valley, and Huanchaco (Chuyo Sanchez 2021; Campaña León and Prieto 2022) in the Moche Valley. Larco Hoyle (1945) also excavated Viru' burials in various Northern Peruvian valleys, especially in the Viru' and Chicama valleys.

Reference: Willey, Gordon R.. Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Peru. Vol. 155. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution, 1953. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/15450>.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245-68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in

the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: *Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection*, 2010.

Reference: Bennett, Wendell C.. *The Gallinazo Group, Viru Valley, Peru*. Vol. 43. *Yale University Publications in Anthropology*. Yale University Press, 1950.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A.. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Cultural Assignations During the Early Intermediate Period: The Case of Huancaco, Virú Valley". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Luis Jaime Castillo and Jeffrey Quilter, 201-22. Washington, D.C.: *Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection*, 2010.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Larco Hoyle, Rafael. *La Cultura Viru*. Sociedad geográfica americana, 1945.

Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Excavations conducted in the Viru' and Moche valleys show that people were buried within residential structures, civic ceremonial buildings, and formal cemeteries (see Bennett 1950; Dillon 2015; Campaña León and Prieto 2022: 77; Millaire and La Torre 2011; Strong and Evans 1952; Willey 1953: 177). A formal cemetery has been identified and excavated in Huanchaco in the Moche Valley (sector Jose' Olaya - Iglesia Colonial; see Sanchez Chuyo 2021). This cemetery is located about 500 meters north of the residential sector (Pampa La Cruz). In this cemetery, individual and multiple burials were identified. 15 out of 22 individuals were buried in the former, while 7 out of 22 individuals were buried in the latter. These burials included

human remains of infants, male, and female individuals ranging between 0-6 months to 50+ years of age. 50% of the individuals (11) were accompanied by grave goods, while the other 50% did not have grave goods. Some individuals found in the Jose' Olaya cemetery stand out and may have had a prominent role in the society. For example, some individuals were placed on reed mats/caskets, wrapped in textiles, and buried with large quantities of grave goods, presence of red pigment on face and pelvis. In addition, the analysis of grave goods and human remains suggests the presence of three broad social/occupational groups: warriors, located at the apex of society, fishermen, and weavers. 16 out of 22 individuals buried in this cemetery were placed in a supine position; this position is usually associated with adult individuals. 19 out of 22 individuals had a N-S orientation. Unlike in the nearby Pampa La Cruz sector, no burials were disturbed and no bones were intentionally added/removed (Sanchez Chuyo 2021).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Willey, Gordon R.. *Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Peru*. Vol. 155. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution, 1953. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/15450>.

Reference: Bennett, Wendell C.. *The Gallinazo Group, Viru Valley, Peru*. Vol. 43. Yale University Publications in Anthropology. Yale University Press, 1950.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A.. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Civic-ceremonial structures called huacas (a very broad term that indicates anything that has a sacred nature, ranging from an unusually shaped rock to a large monumental structure, see Bray 2015) marked the landscape of territories controlled by several Prehispanic Andean cultures, including the Viru' State. In this case, civic-ceremonial structures were mainly built using adobe bricks (see, for example, the main pyramid at Huaca Gallinazo, Huaca Santa Clara, and Huancaco in the Viru' Valley - Bennett 1950; Bourget 2003; Bourget 2010; Millaire 2010; Millaire and Eastaugh 2014; Willey 1953). These monumental structures featured a number of spaces with different functions, such as corridors, burials, kitchens, workshops, storage areas, open areas for gatherings, and small rooms for more private meetings. At Huaca Gallinazo, the main pyramid faces a plaza that may have hosted large gatherings.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Cultural Assignations During the Early Intermediate Period: The Case of Huancaco, Virú Valley". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by

Luis Jaime Castillo and Jeffrey Quilter, 201–22. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245–68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Edward Eastaugh. "Geophysical Survey on the Coast of Peru: The Early Prehispanic City of Gallinazo Group in the Viru Valley". *Latin American Antiquity* 25, no. 3 (September 2014): 239–55. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.25.3.239>.

Reference: Bray, Tamara L., ed.. *The Archaeology of Wak'as: Explorations of the Sacred in the Pre-columbian Andes*. Edited by Tamara L. Bray. University Press of Colorado, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.5876/9781607323181>.

Reference: Bennett, Wendell C.. *The Gallinazo Group, Viru Valley, Peru*. Vol. 43. Yale University Publications in Anthropology. Yale University Press, 1950.

Reference: Willey, Gordon R.. *Prehistoric Settlement Patterns in the Virú Valley, Peru*. Vol. 155. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution, 1953. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/15450>.

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the section about Temples, civic ceremonial buildings included both more secluded spaces for private gatherings and larger plazas. Kitchens, storage areas, food remains (sea mammals, birds, fish, crabs, mollusks, camelids, deer, guinea pigs, snails, peanuts, maize), utilitarian and fine wares further reinforce the idea that banquets took place in these monumental buildings (Bourget 2003; Johns 2017; Masur et al. 2018; Venet-Rogers 2013).

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245–68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Johns, Arwen. *The Richness of Food: A Zooarchaeological Analysis of Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo, North Coast of Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2017.

<https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/4899/>.

Reference: Masur, Lindi, Jean-François Millaire, and Michael Blake. "Peanuts and Power in the Andes: The Social Archaeology of Plant Remains from the Virú Valley, Peru". *Journal of Ethnobiology* 38, no. 4 (2018): 589–609. <https://doi.org/10.2993/0278-0771-38.4.589>.

Reference: Venet-Rogers, Claire. *A Study of Faunal Consumption at the Gallinazo Group Site, Northern Coast of Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2013. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/1749/>.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: A mural painting with a spiral motif was found in a possible storage area at Huancaco (Bourget 2003: 261) while a mural painting depicting fish was found in residential structures adjacent to Huaca Gallinazo (Bennett 1950: 27). Decorated panels with geometric motifs were also found in tapia (rammed earth) walls at sites part of the Gallinazo Group (composed of about 30 mounds - see Bennett 1950: 41).

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245–68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Bennett, Wendell C.. *The Gallinazo Group, Viru Valley, Peru*. Vol. 43. Yale University Publications in Anthropology. Yale University Press, 1950.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the limited sample, it is hard to say if specific features were privileged by the adherents to this cult.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See Temples section.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, the presence of grave goods may indicate this (see Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Chuyo Sanchez 2021; Strong and Evans 1952).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952.
<https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: In few cases, deceased were placed on a mat or in a casket made of reeds. In addition, these individuals may have been wrapped in textiles and accompanied by grave goods (pots, copper plates, gourds, stone tools). At Huaca Santa Clara (Burial 14) the Viru' Valley, one individual was found on the remains of a possible casket (Millaire and La Torre 2003), while at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 the remains of possible reed mats were found next to the cranium of two individuals (Millaire and La Torre 2008). In Huanchaco (Moche Valley), 15% of the individuals were found on reed mats/possible caskets (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 168). It is interesting to note that in Huanchaco two individuals found on reed mats/caskets are the ones that had the highest number of grave goods (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 252), suggesting that individuals placed on mats/caskets may have had a higher status. Deceased placed on reed mats/caskets were found both in residential areas (Huaca Gallinazo V-59, Huaca Santa Clara, Pampa La Cruz in Huanchaco) and in formal cemeteries (Iglesia/ Sectore Jose' Olaya in Huanchaco). The mummification of individuals found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley was likely caused by the very dry environment and not intentional (Millaire and La Torre 2003; Millaire 2016)

Cremation:

– No

Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased whose body was naturally mummified were found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley (Millaire and La Torre 2003; Millaire 2016).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Interment:

– Yes

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

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Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: In very few cases (for example, only 5% of the individuals were flexed in Huanchaco in the Moche Valley - see Campana Leon and Prieto 2022; Sanchez Chuyo 2021 and Millaire and La Torre 2003; 2011 about the Viru' Valley).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the deceased were placed in an extended position, more specifically lying on their back. In some cases, deceased were placed on a bed made of reeds.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245–68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342–58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015.
<https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: The skin of the individual found in Burial 7 at Huaca Santa Clara featured holes likely made by insects. In addition, fly exoskeletons were found around the body (Millaire and La Torre 2003).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú. Lima, Peru, 2003.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Secondary burials were identified in the main pyramid at Huaca Gallinazo in the Viru' Valley (Millaire and La Torre 2003) and at Pampa La Cruz in the Moche Valley (Campana Leon and Prieto 2022).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: A human sacrifice (Burial 9) was found by Millaire (2016) beneath the floor of a gallery-like building at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley. This individual (female, 20-35 years old) was classified as a "retainer sacrifice" and accompanied another female individual (Burial 7 - 20-35 years old). The retainer featured two perimortem blunt force injuries to the occipital region of their cranium (Millaire 2016: 348-349). Burial 13 (female, 45-49 years old) might have also been a retainer of a principal individual (Burial 14, male, 35-40 years old) (Dillon 2015: 107). Another individual (Burial 8 - male, 30-35 years old) may have also been ritually killed. As indicated by perimortem cutmarks identified on a rib, this individual was likely stabbed (Dillon 2015: 105). In the Moche Valley (Huanchaco - sector Pampa La Cruz), the three individuals of the multiple burial PLC 121 and one of the two individuals (E2) found in Tumba 46 may have been sacrificed. These four individuals featured perimortem fractures on their cranium and arms. The individual from Tumba 46 was a 30-35 years old female. The three individuals found in PLC 121 were a 25 years old female, a 38 years old male, and a 6 years old (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 248).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A.. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is not clear if the male individual (Burial 8) found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley was ritually killed or died in combat, isotopic analyses indicated that this person likely spent their childhood in the highlands (Hyland et al. 2021).

Reference: Hyland, Corrie, Jean-François Millaire, and Paul Szpak. "Migration and Maize in the Virú Valley: Understanding Life Histories Through Multi-tissue Carbon, Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Strontium Isotope Analyses". *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 176, no. 1 (September 2021): 21-35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24271>.

In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: Isotopic analyses conducted on the remains of the retainers found by Millaire (2016) at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley indicate that the individuals likely had a coastal diet (Hyland et al. 2021).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Hyland, Corrie, Jean-François Millaire, and Paul Szpak. "Migration and Maize in the Virú Valley: Understanding Life Histories Through Multi-tissue Carbon, Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Strontium Isotope Analyses". *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 176, no. 1 (September 2021): 21-35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24271>.

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: A dog also accompanied the principal individual (Burial 7) identified by Millaire (2016: 348) at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Viru' burials featured a variety of artifacts, including pots, gourds, stone tools, and weapons (see Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Millaire 2016; Sanchez Chuyo 2021).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Thin plates, rings, and fishing hooks made of copper or gilded copper, and gold beads were found both in the Viru' (Strong and Evans 1952: 71-73) and in the Moche (Sanchez Chuyo 2021) valleys.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Decorated (Viru' Negative - see the pottery types called Gallinazo Negative and Carmelo Negative in Strong and Evans 1952: 301-309) and utilitarian pots were found in association with deceased individuals the Viru' and Moche valleys. Textiles, weapons, spindle whorls, gourds, stone tools (e.g., fishing weights) were also found (see Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Millaire and La Torre 2003; Millaire and La Torre 2011; Sanchez Chuyo 2021; Strong and Evans 1952).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Strong, William Duncan, and Clifford Evans. *Cultural Stratigraphy in the Virú Valley Northern Peru*. New York; Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press, 1952. <https://doi.org/10.7312/stro90798>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Organic remains (e.g., peanuts, maize - see Masur et al. 2018; Millaire and La Torre 2003; Millaire and La Torre 2011). Animals (dogs, camelids, frogs, fish) were found in burials in Huanchaco in the Moche Valley (Pampa La Cruz sector) (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 267).

Reference: Masur, Lindi, Jean-François Millaire, and Michael Blake. "Peanuts and Power in the Andes: The Social Archaeology of Plant Remains from the Virú Valley, Peru". *Journal of Ethnobiology* 38, no. 4 (2018): 589–609. <https://doi.org/10.2993/0278-0771-38.4.589>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Excavations conducted in the Viru', Moche, and Chicama valleys tell us that people were buried in a variety of contexts (formal cemeteries, domestic, or civic-ceremonial buildings) and ways (e.g., individual or multiple burials). The vast majority of the individuals were buried in pits in an extended position (however, burials with flexed individuals have also been found) and, in some cases, placed on beds/caskets made of reeds. Most burials feature a N-S orientation. Different positions and orientations were found in formal cemeteries, residential contexts, and civic-ceremonial buildings, so no clear patterns have been discerned so far. Larco Hoyle (1945) also found burials outlined by stone slabs with negative painted pottery (one of the hallmarks of the Viru' state) in the Chicama and Viru' valleys; however, very few contextual information is available about such burials. Excavations yielded both individuals with grave goods and deceased not accompanied by grave goods. The number and type of grave goods found in burials suggests that different social and occupational groups existed (i.e., warriors, fishermen, and weavers). Some burials found at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 in the Viru' Valley by Millaire and La Torre (2011) may represent secondary burials. Some of the burials found in Huanchaco in the Moche Valley (Pampa La Cruz sector) have been disturbed during Prehispanic times, perhaps by the Moche people, who occupied the site after the Viru'. As specified in the "are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial" question of this section and in the Practices section, burials of sacrificed individuals were also found in the Moche and Viru' valleys (see Bourget 2003; Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Larco Hoyle 1945; Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2003; Millaire and La Torre 2008; Millaire and La Torre 2011; Sanchez Chuyo 2021).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2008: Informe Final*. Lima, 2008.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245-68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Larco Hoyle, Rafael. La Cultura Viru. Sociedad geográfica americana, 1945.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: See General Variables - Architecture and Geography section. (Chuyo Sanchez 2021 - Cementerio Jose' Olaya - Iglesia Colonial in Huanchaco, Moche Valley).

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Burials in domestic contexts were found at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 (Millaire and La Torre 2008) and Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley (Millaire 2016), and in Huanchaco in the Moche Valley (sector Pampa La Cruz - see Campaña León and Prieto 2022:76). In the Viru' Valley, individual burials were found in residential areas, while in the Moche Valley both individuals and multiple burials were found in domestic contexts. The deceased were placed in simple pits covered by filling materials (e.g., broken adobes and pots) used as a foundation for a new occupational phase. Such burials are usually between floors/occupational levels. Individuals of different group ages and sexes were interred below occupational floors. These individuals may

have been members of the same family, and this practice may represent an ancestral cult (Campaña León and Prieto 2022: 76; Millaire 2016: 350).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2008: Informe Final. Lima, 2008.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342–58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Burials that possibly marked architectural renewals of civic-ceremonial buildings (see Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2011).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2011: Informe Final. Lima, Peru, 2011.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342–58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The so called Moon Animal (a quadrupedal being - possibly a feline - featuring long claws, well-visible teeth, a long tail and a long protrusion emerging from its head), which appeared in the iconography of various cultures that developed in the northern part of the Central Andes (e.g., Moche, Recuay, Chimu' - see Bruhns 1976; Lau 2002/2004; Mackey and Vogel 2003), was also depicted on two Viru' textiles. In the first case, the animal is at the side of an anthropomorphic being, while in the second case it is not accompanied by other motifs (Surette 2015: 264-266). While the role of this being is not clear, in other Northern Peruvian cultures it was associated with celestial and marine motifs, and scenes representing human sacrifices.

Reference: Mackey, Carol, and Melissa Vogel. "La Luna Sobre Los Andes: Una Revisión Del Animal Lunar". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 325–42. Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Bruhns, Karen. "The Moon Animal in Northern Peruvian Art and Culture". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 14, no. 1 (1976): 21–39. <https://doi.org/10.1179/naw.1976.14.1.002>.

Reference: Lau, George F.. "The Recuay Culture of Peru's North-central Highlands: A Reappraisal of Chronology and Its Implications". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 29, no. 1/2 (2002): 177–202. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3181492>.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the Burial and Afterlife section, a human sacrifice (Burial 9) was found by Millaire (2016) beneath the floor of a gallery-like building at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley. This individual (female, 20-35 years old) was classified as a "retainer sacrifice" and accompanied another female individual (Burial 7 - 20-35 years old). The retainer featured two perimortem blunt force injuries to the occipital region of their cranium (Millaire 2016: 348-349). Burial 13 (female, 45-49 years old) might have also been a retainer of a principal individual (Burial 14, male, 35-40 years old) (Dillon 2015: 107). Another individual (Burial 8 - male, 30-35 years old) may have also been ritually killed. As indicated by perimortem cutmarks identified on a rib, this individual was likely stabbed (Dillon 2015: 105). In Huanchaco (residential sector Pampa La Cruz - Moche Valley), three of the four possibly sacrificed individuals were adults (a 30-35 years old female, a 25 years old female, and a 38 years old male) (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 248).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A.. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As mentioned in the Burial and Afterlife section, Burial 8 found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley may include a young adult male that was ritually killed or died in combat. Isotopic analyses indicated that this person likely spent their childhood in the highlands (Hyland et al. 2021).

Reference: Hyland, Corrie, Jean-François Millaire, and Paul Szpak. "Migration and Maize in the Virú Valley: Understanding Life Histories Through Multi-tissue Carbon, Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Strontium Isotope Analyses". *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 176, no. 1 (September 2021): 21-35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24271>.

↳ Commoners:

– Yes

Notes: At Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley, individuals found in Burial 9 and Burial 13 (possibly sacrificed retainers) showed evidence of systemic stress and severe trauma, suggesting that they may have not been part of the ruling elite (Dillon 2015: 108). It should be noted that no grave goods were buried with the individuals possibly sacrificed in Huanchaco (Pampa La Cruz sector) in the Moche Valley (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 87-94).

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A.. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

↳ Elites:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: One of the individuals possibly sacrificed in Huanchaco (PLC 121 E3 - Pampa La Cruz sector) in the Moche Valley was 6 years old that was likely hit in the head (bregma) with a blunt object (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 248).

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No grave goods were buried with the 6 years old child (Sanchez Chuyo 2021: 93).

↳ Elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that people participated in rituals that were carried out in monumental structures (such as the pyramid at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 in the Viru' Valley and the plaza located in front of it) and in more restricted spaces (such as smaller gathering areas identified at Huaca Santa Clara and open areas connected by labyrinth-like corridors at Huancaco in the Viru' Valley) (see Bourget 2003; Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2012).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245-68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2012: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2012.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Small-scale rituals may have involved the veneration of ancestral figures (see burials beneath the floors - see Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Millaire 2016). Propitiatory rituals may have also been carried out in such spaces. For example, at Huaca Santa Clara decorated pots were smashed on purpose when the gallery-like room that yielded a burial and sacrifice was being built (Millaire 2016: 350-358).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that people participated in rituals that were carried out in monumental structures (such as the pyramid at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 and the plaza located in front of it, Huaca Santa Clara, and at Huancaco in the Virú Valley) (see Bourget 2003; Bourget 2010; Millaire 2010; Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2012). At Huaca Gallinazo V-59, excavations carried out in residential compounds and in the main pyramid showed that libations/feasts were likely taking place in the latter. In addition, differences in consumption practices were identified. For example, deer and snails were only consumed in the main pyramid and this civic-ceremonial building yielded larger bone fragments compared to the residential areas (see Venet-Rogers 2013). At Huancaco, Bourget (2003; 2010) identified structures located on three different levels. The lower and middle part of the complex featured food preparation areas, while the upper part featured an open space (595 square meters) for the consumption of food and beverages using decorated pots. Beverages and food may have also been presented to a figure sitting on a roofed pyramidal structure. A restricted number of people may have also participated in more restricted ceremonies carried out in two smaller areas (19,4 and 6,12 square meters).

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Cultural Assignations During the Early Intermediate Period: The Case of Huancaco, Virú Valley". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Luis Jaime Castillo and Jeffrey Quilter, 201-22. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Somos Diferentes: Dinámica Ocupacional Del Sitio Castillo De Huancaco, Valle De Virú". In *Moche: Hacia El Final Del Milenio - Tomo I*, edited by Santiago Uceda and Elias Mujica, 245-68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Arqueológico Virú Temporada 2012: Informe Final*. Lima, Peru, 2012.

Reference: Venet-Rogers, Claire. *A Study of Faunal Consumption at the Gallinazo Group Site, Northern Coast of Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2013. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/1749/>.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Land snails (*Scutalus* sp.) were found in the main pyramid at Huaca Gallinazo V-59 in the Viru' Valley (Venet-Rogers 2013) and they may have been used for their psychoactive properties (Bourget 1990). The analyses conducted on the teeth of the individual found in Burial 13 at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley suggest that this person was likely a coca-chewer (Dillon 2015: 88). In addition, evidence from human remains found at Cerro Oreja (a site located in the middle Moche Valley that yielded Viru' Negative pottery) suggests that this ritually important plant was consumed (even though in smaller quantities compared to the previous occupational phase) by people living at this site (Gagnon et al. 2013).

Reference: Bourget, Steve. "Caracoles Sagrados En La Iconografía Moche". *Gaceta Arqueológica Andina* 5, no. 20 (1990): 45-58.

Reference: Gagnon, Celeste M., Brian R. Billman, José Carcelén, and Karl J. Reinhard. "Tracking Shifts in Coca Use in the Moche Valley: Analysis of Oral Health Indicators and Dental Calculus Microfossils". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 33, no. 2 (2013): 193-214. <https://doi.org/10.1179/0077629713Z.0000000009>.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: Tattoos (geometric drawings on the face) have been identified on the principal individual (Burial 7 - female, 20-35 years old) found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley (Millaire 2016). The female individual that was likely sacrificed (Burial 9 - 20-35 years old) and accompanied Burial 7 also featured tattoos (in this case, linear tattoos on the wrists and ankles) (see Dillon 2015; Millaire 2016; Millaire and La Torre 2003).

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Estuardo La Torre. *Proyecto Huaca Santa Clara: Temporada 2003. Variabilidad Social, Económica Y Cultural En El Intermedio Temprano: La Comunidad Gallinazo Del Sitio Santa Clara En El Valle De Virú, Costa Norte Del Perú*. Lima, Peru, 2003.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Posts and Pots: Propitiatory Ritual at Huaca Santa Clara in the Virú Valley, Peru". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Klaus D. Haagen and Marla J. Toyne, 342-58. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/309377.20>.

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A. *Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London,

↳ Circumcision:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Food taboos:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Hair:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:
– Yes

Notes: Makowski (2009) argues that Viru' individuals may have worn headdresses with stepped motifs, feathers, felines, and back flaps that resembled Moche headdresses. As regards textiles, also in this case Viru' and Moche people shared several iconographic motifs (steps, waves, warriors, fishes, possible supernatural beings). However, these motifs show slight differences that might indicate ideological diversity (Surette 2015).

Reference: Surette, Flannery. Virú and Moche Textiles on the North Coast of Peru During the Early Intermediate Period: Material Culture, Domestic Traditions and Elite Fashions. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2829/>.

Reference: Makowski, Krzysztof. "Virú-moche Relations: Technological Identity, Stylistic Preferences, and the Ethnic Identity of Ceramic Manufacturers and Users". In Gallinazo: An Early Cultural Tradition on the Peruvian North Coast, edited by Jean-François Millaire and Magali Morlion, 33–61. Los Angeles, CA: UCLA Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2009. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2tk8b0wc>.

↳ Ornaments:
– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some individuals found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley (including Burial 7 and Burial 14, possible principal individuals accompanied by sacrificed retainers) display a fronto-occipital/tabular cranial deformation (see Dillon 2015). However, it has been argued that such deformation may have not indicated an affiliation with a specific social, religious or ethnic group (Torres-Rouff 2020).

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A. Ritual Violence and Times of Transition: A Bioarchaeological

Reference: Dillon, Rebecca A. *ritual violence and times of transition: A bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo in the Virú Valley, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2015. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2724/>.

Reference: Torres-Rouff, Christina. "Cranial Modification and the Shapes of Heads Across the Andes". *International Journal of Paleopathology* 29 (June 2020): 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpp.2019.06.007>.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some individuals found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley (including Burial 7 and 14, possible principal individuals accompanied by sacrificed retainers) display a fronto-occipital/tabular cranial deformation (see Dillon 2015). However, such deformation may have not indicated affiliation with a specific religious, social, or ethnic group (see Torres-Rouff 2013: 98).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The state featured a four-tiered settlement system. At the top was the capital city Gallinazo Group, followed by administrative and defensive centers (castillos, located at the Viru' Valley neck), villages, and hamlets (Millaire et al. 2016). Evidence from excavations and burial practices suggests that Viru' society was ruled by an elite (see Downey 2014; Millaire 2010a; Millaire 2010b; Millaire et al. 2016)

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Primary State Formation in the Virú Valley, North Coast of Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107, no. 14 (February 22, 2010): 6186–91. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0911226107>.

Reference: Downey, Jordan T.. *Statecraft in the Virú Valley, Peru, in the First Millennium A.D.*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2014. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2687/>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016–25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents to this group interact with the Viru' state institution. Like in many other Prehispanic Andean cultures, politics and religion were likely inextricably connected, and bureaucratic figures may have also had a religious role (Quilter 2022).

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey. *The Ancient Central Andes*. 2nd ed.. Routledge, 2022.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Viru' state arranged the construction of storage facilities at administrative sites like Huaca Santa Clara and perhaps at Huaca Gallinazo in the Viru' Valley (Millaire 2010). At Huaca Santa Clara, several storage rooms (5 to 7 cubic meters of storage space) with food remains (maize, beans, peanuts, peppers, and fruits) were identified.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As argued by Downey (2014), the spread and the increase in the number and spatial extent of settlements in the Viru' Valley during the Early Intermediate Period (ca. 200 BCE - 600 CE) suggest a substantial expansion of irrigation networks and an increase in the amount of arable land available to the inhabitants of the valley. The emergence of a centralized power may have facilitated the construction and maintenance of such public works.

Reference: Downey, Jordan T.. *Statecraft in the Virú Valley, Peru, in the First Millennium A.D.*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2014. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2687/>.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Millaire (2010) suggested that the storage facilities found at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley may have stored goods possibly acquired through a system of tribute.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Warfare was likely an important part of the members of the Viru' state and its members. The northward expansion (see Makowski 2009; Millaire et al 2016) suggests that the state likely had an organized army. The importance of warfare is also revealed by pots decorated with modeled warriors (Millaire 2009: 3), clay war maces that decorated civic-ceremonial buildings (Millaire 2010), burials with spear throwers and/or wooden/copper war maces found in the Moche (Campaña León and Prieto 2022 and Sanchez Chuyo 2021) and in the Viru' (Strong and Evans 1952: 71-73) valleys. The Viru' state also built six castillos or fortresses (that likely had also civic-ceremonial functions) that controlled the Viru' Valley neck and protected the coastal part of this valley. In addition, they suggest that there may have been tensions with people living in the intermediate zones and in the highlands (Downey 2014: 185-188; Millaire 2008; Sghinolfi 2021).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Sánchez Chuyo, Litzley Shannen. *Prácticas Funerarias Virú En La Bahía De Huanchaco, Valle Bajo De Moche - Costa Norte Del Perú*. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2021.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016–25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Makowski, Krzysztof. "Virú-moche Relations: Technological Identity, Stylistic Preferences, and the Ethnic Identity of Ceramic Manufacturers and Users". In *Gallinazo: An Early Cultural Tradition on the Peruvian North Coast*, edited by Jean-François Millaire and Magali Morlion, 33–61. Los Angeles, CA: UCLA Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2009. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2tk8b0wc>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Gallinazo and the Tradición Norcosteña". In *Gallinazo: An Early Cultural Tradition on the Peruvian North Coast*, edited by Jean-François Millaire and Magali Morlion, 1–17. Los Angeles, CA: UCLA Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2009. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2tk8b0wc>.

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Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "Moche Political Expansionism as Viewed from Virú: Recent Archaeological Work in the Close Periphery of a Hegemonic City-state System". In *New Perspectives on Moche Political Organization*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and Luis Jaime Castillo. Washington, D.C.:

Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection, 2010.

Reference: Sghinolfi, Amedeo. *Life in Between: Prehispanic Settlement Patterns of the Carabamba Valley, Northern Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2021. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/8318/>.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See previous answer

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: For more information on the foods consumed by the Viru' people, see Campaña León and Prieto 2022; Johns 2017; Masur et al. 2018; Millaire 2010; Szpak et al. 2014; Venet-Rogers 2013).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Johns, Arwen. *The Richness of Food: A Zooarchaeological Analysis of Huaca Santa Clara and Huaca Gallinazo, North Coast of Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2017. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/4899/>.

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Reference: Szpak, Paul, Jean-François Millaire, Christine D. White, and Fred J. Longstaffe. "Small Scale Camelid Husbandry on the North Coast of Peru (virú Valley): Insight from Stable Isotope Analysis". *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 36 (December 2014): 110–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2014.08.005>.

Reference: Venet-Rogers, Claire. *A Study of Faunal Consumption at the Gallinazo Group Site, Northern Coast of Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2013. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/1749/>.

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Elias Mujica, 245–68. Trujillo, Peru: Universidad Nacional de Trujillo and Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú - Fondo Editorial, 2003.

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Reference: Virú State Religion, Spencer, Charles S.. "Territorial Expansion and Primary State Formation". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107, no. 16 (January 24, 2010): 7119–26. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1002470107>.

Reference: Virú State Religion, Downey, Jordan T.. *Statecraft in the Virú Valley, Peru, in the First Millennium A.D.*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2014. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/2687/>.

Reference: Virú State Religion, Millaire, Jean-François, Gabriel Prieto, Flannery Surette, Elsa M. Redmond, and Charles S. Spencer. "Statecraft and Expansionary Dynamics: A Virú Outpost at Huaca Prieta, Chicama Valley, Peru". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 41 (September 26, 2016): E6016–25. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609972113>.

Reference: Virú State Religion, Millaire, Jean-François, and Edward Eastaugh. "Ancient Urban Morphology in the Virú Valley, Peru: Remote Sensing Work at the Gallinazo Group (100 B.C.–A.D. 700)". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 36, no. 4 (2011): 289–97. <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346911X13200731373908>.

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